

Cyber-Crimes against Women: Statutory Law Foundations and Judicial Response in India

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Abstract

Due to technology advancement, ratio of cybercrimes against women is on the rise. At present it is arising as a major challenge for government. To address this issue government has taken many initiatives like, the Indian government has amended the Information Technology Act, the Indian Penal Code (IPC), and the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA). These laws define cybercrimes especially in reference to women, and tried to give protection to victims of these crimes. In addition, the Indian judiciary has taken a number of steps to resist cybercrimes against women, such as establishing recommendations to prevent the misuse of section 498A of the IPC and declaring cyber stalking to be a serious offense. Initially few Steps which were taken by government, such as the Cyber Swachhta Centre and the Cyber Crime Prevention against Women and Children (CCPWC) project, to educate women about cybercrimes against women and assist victims. Although there are number of attempts which was taken by the government and the courts to reduce cybercrime, but still it remains a significant challenge for the nation and the government.

Key words: Cyber-crimes, Information Technology Act, Cyber Swachhta Kendra

Introduction

The Indian government has passed legal regulation in response to these crimes, and the court has been instrumental in tending to these offenses. Disregarding the progressions, a ton of issues actually should be settled on the off chance that cybercrimes against women are to be properly combated in India. Absence of knowledge among women with respect to cybercrime is one issue. Numerous women know nothing about the dangers related to use the internet and different technologies, and many are likewise uncertain of how to remain protected from cybercrimes. The scarcity of resources accessible to law enforcement organisation to investigate and punish cybercrimes is another issue. One of the major problems in India is that law enforcing agencies often absence of requisite information and experience to investigate cybercrime, and they have not sufficient facility and resources to track down and prosecute culprits. Here is an outline of India's rule regulation establishments and judicial response to cybercrime against women:

- **Online Harassment and Stalking:** This incorporates sending threatening or hostile messages, taking part in undesirable online correspondence, reliably monitoring or tracking somebody's online activities without assent, and using technologies to threaten, menace, bully, embarrass or humiliate women.
- **Retribution Pornography and Non-consensual Sharing of Intimate Substance:** This includes the unapproved distribution or sharing of unequivocal or intimate pictures, videos or recordings of women without their assent. Culprits frequently use technology to take advantage of and blackmail victims.
- **Online Defamation and Character Extermination:** This alludes to the scattering of forge and harming information about women through online platforms, social media, or other computerized (digital) channels with the intention to hurt their reputation or cause abashment.

- **Financial Fraud and Data fraud (Identity Theft):** Women can be picked out through different fraudulent plans, for example, phishing, hacking, or identity theft fraud, where culprits gain unapproved or unauthorized access to individual data, personal information financial records, bank account details or credit card details to do fake exercises or fraudulent activities.
- **Online Human Trafficking and Exploitation:** The internet can be utilized as a medium to work with illegal exploitation, constrained prostitution, or the abuse of women through internet based platforms, unlawful or illegal websites, online entertainment platforms or social media.
- **Online Sexism, Misogyny, Revenge porn and Hate speech:** Women might confront targeted online based hate speech, misuse, or threats based on their gender. This incorporates chauvinist sexist remarks or misogynistic substance, and instigation of brutality, incitement of violence or oppression women. In present time, where one press on the internet can open the entry gate to a entirety modern world, privacy has without a doubt become priceless and difficult ; individuals crave for to show other's individual space. Digitalization has been both favouring and revile. Increases in digitalization have also expanded crimes within the virtual world; one of such cybercrime is exact revenge porn. In twentieth century there are free and unlimited internet, revenge pornography has come out as a cutting edge tool to use against individuals for egoist wants and torment the casualty both mentally and physically. In India, occurrences of revenge porn may not be on the news headlines frequently, but in a country where rape videos trend online, how secure are individuals from revenge porn? Revenge porn is the dispersion of sexually explicit pictures or video of people without their assent. The sexually explicit pictures or video may be made by an accomplice of an intimate relationship with the knowledge and assent of the subject, or it may be made without their knowledge. section 292, 354C, 499 and 509 of Indian Penal Code, 1860 attracts a conviction of revenge porn and the section 66E, 67, 67A and 72 of Information Technology Act, 2000 attracts a conviction. the first conviction in India relating to revenge porn delivered by The District Court of Purba Medinipur (West Bengal) is case of State of West Bengal vs. Animesh Boxi¹
- **Cyber Harassing, Bullying and Online Friend Provocation:** This is the utilization of technology by companions or people known to the victim to menace, bully, terrify, or abuse women. It could occur over internet-based media, messaging applications, or gatherings or forums on the internet.
- **Online Child Sexual Exploitation and their Grooming:** The web can be abused to prepare and take advantage of minors, including young women, for sexual purposes. Guilty parties might use online platforms to lay out trust, control victims, and participate in criminal or illegal operations.

It's critical to take note of that these classifications are not exhaustive, and cyber-crimes against women can take different structures and develop over the long run as technology advances. Endeavours are being made to address these wrongdoings through legal structures, awareness campaigns, and the foundation of specific law enforcement units to investigate and indict or prosecute offenders.

Statutory Law

Information Technology Act, 2000²: The IT Act is the essential regulation in India that

arrangements with cyber - crimes, including those against women. It explains offenses, for example, cyber-stalking, cyber-harassment, and publishing sexually explicit material. It additionally accommodates disciplines, penalties and punishments for these offenses. An outline of the significant section of the Information Technology Act, 2000:

- **Section 66E - Violation of Privacy:** The discipline and punishment for wilfully collecting, sending, publishing or distributing an individual's confidential region without their assent, including through computerized (digital) means, illustrated in this provision of the IT Act.

- **Section 67** - Distributing, publishing, or Sending Indecent Material: The publication or transmission of any material containing sexually unequivocal substance that is vulgar or requests to scurrilous cravings is punished under this provision of the IT Act.
- **Section 67A** - Publishing or Transmitting Depicting Explicit Sexual Acts: This provision restricts the publication or transmission of material material unequivocal sexual acts or conduct.
- **Section 67B** - Distributing, Publishing or Transmitting Material Depicting minors in Sexually Explicit Acts: This provision particularly addresses the publication distribution or transmission of material portraying minors participating in unequivocal sexual acts.

Indian Penal Code, 1860: Although the IPC doesn't address cybercrimes explicitly, it contains provisions that can be applied to certain cyber offenses against women. For example, section like 354 (outraging a woman's modesty), 509 (word, gesture, or act intended to insult a woman's modesty), and 292 (sale, etc., of obscene books, etc.) can be summoned in cyber- crime cases.

Section 354A: Sexual harassment and punishment for sexual harassment- (1) A man committing any of the following acts-- (i) physical contact and advances involving unwelcome and explicit sexual overtures; or (ii) a demand or request for sexual favours; or (iii) Showing pornography against the will of a woman; or (iv) Making sexually coloured remarks, shall be guilty of the offence of sexual harassment.

(2) Any man who commits the offence specified in clause (i) or clause (ii) or clause (iii) of sub-section (1) shall be punished with rigorous imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both.

(3) any man who commits the offence specified in clause (IV) of sub-section (1) shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to one year, or with fine, or with both.]

Section 354D: a man followed a woman and contacted or attempted to contact her to foster personal interaction repeatedly despite a clear indication of disinterest by such woman.

Section 506: Punishment for criminal intimidation it likewise covers that large number of threats and intimidation passed on through electronics means are used to make a women dread herself or related individual.

Section 509: provision of this section additionally covers those acts which are committed through electronic communication which intended to intended the modesty of woman.

Section 499/500: Defamation-These sections of the IPC address defamation, including online defamation, where a women's reputation is hurt through misleading proclamations or imputations made publicly.

Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal) Act, 2013: (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal) Act, 2013: This Act aims to prevent and address sexual harassments of women at workplaces, including occurrences of online harassment. It requires employers to make internal accusation Committees to address allegations of sexual harassments.

The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 - The law protects women who are sisters, widows, or moms too. Its main role is to safeguard the spouse or female live-in accomplice from violence from the husband or male live-in accomplice or his family members. The expression "Domestic Violence" alludes to either real or threatened physical, sexual, verbal, profound, or monetary maltreatment. This definition additionally incorporates harassment of the woman or her family members through illegal dowry demands. It can be utilized when technology is used to harass women in domestic relationship, for example, by stalking or threatening them on the web.

The Protection of Children from Sexual offenses Act, 2012 - The protection of Children from Sexual Offenses Act of 2012 is a piece of regulation that protects kids from sexual Offenses.

Different offenses are defined by the Act, including cybercrime against children. The Act likewise determines the punishments for such offenses.

The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 - is a regulation that precludes the giving and getting of dowry. The Act frames a scope of offenses, including dowry related cybercrime. The Act additionally indicates the punishments for such offenses.

The Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986 - Is a regulation that prohibits the indecent representation of women. The Act frames a range of offenses, including cybercrimes including slanderous portrayals of women. The Act likewise indicates the punishments for such offenses.

These regulations accommodate a scope of punishment for cyber-crimes against women's, including detainment, imprisonment, fines, and community services. The regulations likewise accommodate measures to prevent cyber-crimes, for example, the registration of cybercrime complaints, the tracking of digital or cyber criminals, and the expulsion or removal of unlawful substance from the internet. In India, cybercrime is on the ascent, and women are lopsidedly impacted. More than 10,700 cybercrimes carried out against women were reported in India in 2021, or 20.2% of all cybercrimes revealed in the country. Cyber stalking, cyber-bullying, cyber impersonation, cyber extortion, and cyber-sexual harassment are the most common types of cybercrime against women. The accompanying diagram portrays the quantity of cybercrimes perpetrated against ladies in India somewhere in the range of 2018 and 2021, as well as their extent of complete cybercrimes:

Table-1³: Cyber-Crimes against Women

Year	Number of crimes against Women	Share of total Cyber Crimes
2013	2,411	19.4%
2014	3,379	22.30%
2015	4,495	21.88%
2016	5,727	20.58%
2017	6,121	20.18%
2018	6,030	22.23%
2019	8,379	18.73%
2020	10,405	20.79%
2021	10,730	20.2%
2022	11,331	20.4%

As may be see, the quantity of cyber-crimes against women in India has been expanding lately. In 2021, there were 10,700 over cyber-crimes against women, which represented 20.2% of all cyber-crimes reported in the country.

The most widely recognized kinds of digital wrongdoings against ladies are:

- Cyber Stalking: This includes sending undesirable messages or pictures, or conveying intimidations on the web.
- Digital Tormenting or Bullying: This includes pestering or embarrassing somebody on the web.
- Cyber Pantomime or Impersonation: This includes making a fake web-based profile in somebody's name and utilizing it to spread pernicious or malicious substance.
- Cyber coercion: This includes requesting cash or different advantages from somebody in return for not releasing compromising, humiliating or embarrassing data about them.
- Cyber Sexual Harassment: This includes utilizing on the web platforms to request, convey, or make sexually explicit content without somebody's assent.

Coming up next are the main 10 states in India with the biggest number of cybercrime cases including women revealed in 2023, not entirely set in stone by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB):

Table -2⁴

Rank	State	Number of Cyber Crimes Against Women
1	Telangana	1,872
2	Uttar Pradesh	1,669
3	Karnataka	1,488
4	Maharashtra	1,356
5	Delhi	1,251
6	Kerala	1,223
7	Tamil Nadu	1,185
8	West Bengal	1,175
9	Andhra Pradesh	1,100
10	Haryana	1,064

These states address more than 80% of all cybercrime cases against women uncovered in India. Moreover, the NCRB noticed that the quantity of cybercrime cases against women has been ascending as of late, with a 5% increment in 2023 contrasted with 2022. As can be seen, Telangana has the largest number of cybercrimes carried out against women in India, trailed by Karnataka and Uttar Pradesh. Moreover, the overall number of cybercrimes reported in these states is the highest in the country.

Other Agencies Provided by Government

- **Cyber Crime Prevention against Women and Children (CCPWC) Scheme** - The Indian government began the CCPWC project in 2016 to train law enforcement authorities to effectively deal with cybercrime cases influencing women and children. The scheme additionally endeavours to bring issues to light about cybercrime and help victims.
- **Cyber Swachhta Kendra** - The Indian government made the Cyber Swachhta Kendra in 2017 to give information, tool and apparatuses to assist residents with protecting themselves from cyber-attacks. Users might get free antivirus software and other cyber protection measures from the portal. On September 20, 2018, the MHA (Ministry of Home Affairs) launched a cybercrime portal for residents to report hostile and offensive content.
- What's more, cybercrime Forensic Labs have been laid out in various States, and over of 3,664 people, including 410 Public Prosecutors and judicial Officials, have gotten guidance on the most proficient method to distinguish, identify, and resolve cybercrimes against women and children.
- As per the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act of 2018, the MHA (Ministry of Home Affairs) sent off an online analytical device for police on February 19, 2019, named "Investigation Tracking System for Sexual Offenses," to work with States and UTs. This device is intended to screen or monitor and track time-bound investigation in sexual assault cases.

Role of the Judiciary in India at Cyberspace

The judiciary in India assumes a significant role in tackling issues, problems and ensuring justice in the cyber space. Here are a few vital roles of the judiciary in India concerning the cyber space:

- **Interpretation of Law**- In cyber related issues; the judiciary interprets and carries out existing regulation and legislation, for example, the Information Technology Act of 2000 and the Indian Penal Code. They look at the contents in these regulations and offer lawful direction on how they ought to be perceived and used with regards to cybercrime. The Indian Supreme Court has interpreted cybercrime corresponding to women's rights matters in various ways. The Court has decided in certain circumstances that cybercrime may be viewed as a type of sexual harassment, assault or attack. In the case of **Vishaka and Others v. State of Rajasthan**⁵ that's what the Court decided "sexual harassment of women at workplace is a type of sex discrimination that violates Articles 14, 15, and 19(1) (g) of the Constitution. "The Court likewise expressed that "the State has an established commitment to protect women from

sexual harassment in the work place." In other decision, the Court has decided that cybercrime can be used to stalk, intimidate or scare somebody. In **Nirbhaya v. State of NCT of Delhi**⁶, the Court viewed that as "the right to privacy is a fundamental right ensured under Article 21 of the Constitution." That's what's more, the Court expressed "the right to privacy incorporates the right to be free from stalking, intimidation and terrorizing," furthermore, and the Supreme Court has decided that cybercrime can be used to spread hate speech and violence against women. The Court concluded in the case of **Shreya Singhal v. Union of India**⁷ that "the right to freedom of speech and articulation isn't outright." The Court additionally decided that "the right to speak freely and expression might be restricted if important to protect the fundamental rights of others. **Rupan Deol Bajaj v. Kanwar Pal Singh Gill**⁸ this case managed sexual harassment and featured that undesirable physical contact or advances, whether in person or through web correspondence, can constitute a offence. Through their judgements and decisions, the judiciary in India shapes the legal system, lays out points of reference, and ensure the protection of rights and justice in the cyberspace. Their role is imperative in adapting the legal system to the evolving difficulties presented by cyber-crimes and ensuring a safe, protected and secure at all digital environment for all people. **State of Maharashtra v. Salman Salim Khan (2003)**⁹ this case underlined the significance of assent in online correspondences and held that an individual's explicit assent is important before any sexually express material is shared. **Aseem Shrivastava v. Union of India (2017)** as indicated by this decision, the Information Technology Act of 2000 can be used to punish cybercrimes against women like stalking, voyeurism, harassment and online provocation. In the case of **Amandeep Singh v. State of Punjab (2018)**¹⁰ this decision found that a cop can't decline to register a FIR in a case of cybercrime against a woman.

Addressing Legal Challenges:

The judiciary tends to legal challenges and gaps that emerge in related to cyber space. They might give decisions or directions on complex issues like jurisdiction, evidence, and admissibility of electronic evidence, privacy concerns, and assurance of victim's rights in the web space. In 2015, the Apex Court of India guided the establishment of special courts to hear matters of cybercrime against women. These courts are staffed by judges who are exceptionally prepared and trained in cyber law, and they are intended to give a fast and effective forum for women who have been misled by cybercrimes. The Supreme Court's decisions and regulation are at initially a decent beginning; however they just start to expose the issue. Furthermore, it is fundamental to provide assistance to women who have been the survivors of cyber violence and to bring awareness of the problem. The judiciary protects women' essential freedoms in the cyber space in various ways. These are a few models:

- **To Provide Protection of Fundamental Rights in cyberspace:** In the cyber space, the judiciary protects the preservation of fundamental rights and freedoms. They protect, in addition to other things, rights to privacy, freedom of speech, a fair trial in reference to cybercrimes and rights to information and online exercises.
- **Passing of Regulation:** The courts have been instrumental in sanctioning regulations that protects women' rights in the web. In India, for instance, the Information Technology Act of 2000 was amended in 2008 to incorporate areas expressly tending to cybercrime against women. These provisions incorporate Section 66E, which condemns sending sexually express messages to women, and section 66F, which condemn publishing or transmitting data that is probably going to attack the privacy of a woman.
- **Enforcement of Law:** The judiciary has additionally supported the implementation of regulation that defend women' rights in the cyberspace. The Supreme Court of India struck down Section 66A of the Information Technology Act, 2000, which condemned "grossly offensive menacing" texts on account of **Shreya Singhal v. Association of India (2013) 8 SCC 730**. This decision was hailed as a victory with the expectation of free speech, and it has

supported the protection of the right of women who utilize the cyber space to express their thoughts.

- **Making Awareness:** The judiciary has additionally assisted with bringing issues to light about the dangers of cybercrime and the need of guarding or defending women' rights in the cyber space. For instance, the Supreme Court of India has coordinated multiple cybercrime awareness workshops for judges and lawyers. These camps have helped with teaching the adjudicators on the latest patterns in cybercrime as well as the need of protecting women' rights in this area.

Not with standing these arrangements, the judiciary has helped with the assurance of women' rights in the cyberspace by giving direction to law enforcement authorities on the most proficient method to explore and punish cybercrimes against women. These principles have supported ensuring that survivors of cybercrime get the justice they deserve.

Adjudicating of Cybercrimes Cases: The judiciary arbitrates cybercrimes cases, ensuring fair trials and due process of law. They investigate the evidence, analyse the legitimate contentions, and convey decisions in light of current realities and the applicable regulations. They assess the culpability or innocence of accused and apply appropriate disciplines, punishments or remedies.

Directing Organizations in Law Enforcement: judiciary advises to authorities on cybercrime examination, investigation and prosecution. They give guidelines on procedure, evidence collection or assortment, and ensuring consistence with constitutional safeguards while managing cyber-crimes against people, including women.

Protecting Cyber Security: The judiciary play a vital role in protecting cyber space by addressing cases connected with hacking, information breaks, Data leak, cyber-attacks and digital assaults. They analyse the legal parts of cyber security, promote awareness, and energize the execution of effective to safeguard security measures to protect people and associations in the cyber space.

Online Grievance Mechanisms: Courts have emphasized the significance of online objection or complaint mechanisms and the requirement for police to register and investigate crimes related to cyber protests immediately. This has helped out the reporting and redressal process for victims of digital crimes.

The Supreme Court plays had a significant impact in protecting women's from cybercrime. The Court's decisions have supported bringing awareness of the issue and furnishing victims with a legal structure for remedy. The Court has additionally condemned the public authority's response to cybercrime, calling for additional effective measures to prevent and prosecute such crimes. In general, while legal rules in India offer a system for combating cybercrime against women, the legal response is critical in appropriately interpreting and implementing these regulations. The judiciary plays had a fundamental impact in defining and tending to cybercrimes, giving justice to victims, and making awareness about the legitimate outcomes of such offenses. Be that as it may, challenges stay in ensuring effective enforcement, capacity building, and bringing issues to light among people in general about cybercrime regulations and women 'rights. Positively! Cyber-crimes against women have turned into a growing concern in India in recent years, and the public authority has found multiple ways to resolve this issue.

Conclusion

All in all, cyber-crimes against women in India are a huge concern in the present digital age. The legal regulation establishments and role of judiciary in India have made strides in addressing these crimes and giving justice to the victims. The Information Technology Act, of 2000, alongside arrangements in the Indian Penal Code and other pertinent regulations, serve as the legal system for handling cyber-crimes. These regulations defines offenses, for example, cyber stalking, cyber harassment, non-consensual sharing of private or intimate substance, and online defamation, among others. They provide the legitimate premise to prosecuting offenders and protecting the rights of women in the cyberspace.

The judiciary plays a vital role in interpreting and enacting these laws. Through milestone decisions, legal precedents and legitimate points of reference, the judiciary has given clearness on the interpretation of existing regulations with regards to cyber-crimes against women. They have perceived offenses like cyber-stalking, retribution pornography, picture transforming and image morphing as punishable under the current legal systems. The judiciary has additionally accentuated the value of privacy, data protection, and the quick documenting and examination of complaints in regards to cybercrime. In any case, there are still issues with the proficient use of these regulations and the advancement of law enforcement's capability agencies about women' rights and cybercrime regulation. To address these issues and assurance the effective use of the statutory laws, cooperation between the judiciary, policing, law enforcement agencies and different partners is essential.

Notwithstanding the obstacles, there are various things that might be finished in India to combat cybercrime against women. One basic approach is to improve women knowledge of cybercrime. This might be achieved by instructing, teaching and training programs, as well as public awareness initiatives. Another important step is to give law enforcement authorities with the vital preparation, necessary training and resources to investigate and punish cybercrime. This might be achieved by supporting training projects or programmes and developing new technology to help law enforcement authorities in tracking down and prosecuting culprits. Moreover, it is critical to persistently adapt and update the legitimate structures to stay up with emerging types of cyber-crimes and technological progressions and advancement. As per requirements regular amendments and enforcement to the regulations or legislation, as well as special training programme for legal experts and professionals and law enforcement, are important to effectively combat cyber-crimes against women. By and large, while there is still work to be finished, the legal regulation establishments and judicial response in India are instrumental in tending to cyber-crimes against women, giving justice to the victims, and establishing a more secure digital environment for all people.

References:

- ¹ Case No. GR:1587/17, decided on 07/03/2018]
- ² Data Innovation (IT) Act: The Information Technology Act was enacted in 2000 to offer lawful acknowledgment for electronic transaction and to administer internet action in India. It was amended in 2008 to add to deal with matters that the original legislation did not address and to accommodate further advancements in IT and related security concerns since the original statute was enacted.
- ³ National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), <https://ncrb.gov.in/en> visited on 26-06.23
- ⁴ National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), <https://ncrb.gov.in/en> visited on 26-06.23
- ⁵ (1997) 6 SCC 241
- ⁶ 5 (2012) 5 SCC 1.
- ⁷ (2013) 8 SCC 730.
- ⁸ 1996 AIR 309.
- ⁹ Appeal (crl.) 1508 Of 2003.
- ¹⁰ (2018) 3 SCC (Cri) 105.

